

Impact Assessment of Prolonged Quarantine on Senior High School Students in a State College in Zamboanga City, Philippines

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ABSTRACT: This study utilized descriptive-quantitative research design to determine the impact of prolonged quarantine on senior high school students in a State College in Zamboanga City, Philippines. There were 200 senior high school students answered the researcher-made instrument Prolonged Quarantine Impact Questionnaire. Result revealed that during the prolonged quarantine, students were able to strengthen their faith in God and spend more time for their selves, family and friends. More so, there were changes in the sleeping pattern on students and they invest their time in new hobbies. When data were grouped according to sex, grade level and track, result revealed that significant difference exist.

KEYWORDS: Prolonged Quarantine, Impact Assessment, Covid-19, Senior High School

INTRODUCTION

The 2019 coronavirus disease or COVID-19 was declared as a worldwide health emergency on January 30, 2020 and was considered as the biggest outbreak of a typical pneumonia since the SARS outbreak in 2003 (Gallegos, 2020). The symptoms of the virus ranged from mild to severe illnesses, which may appear after 2-14 days from the initial exposure to the virus (WebMD, 2021). In response to this health threat, the City Government of Zamboanga issued Executive Order No. BC 552-2020 which limited all public meetings, imposed strict movement restrictions and postponed face to face classes. More so, the entire Philippines was placed under state of calamity through President Proclamation No. 929, wherein, the following policies were implemented: price control of basic needs and commodities, granting interest-free loans, distribution of calamity funds, authorization of importation and receipt of donations, and hazard allowance for public health workers and government personnel in the fields of science and technology (Official Gazette of the Republic of the Philippines, 2020).

Different types of community quarantine status have been introduced to combat the spread of the virus. Enhanced Community Quarantine (ECQ) imposed stricter lockdowns that prohibits the use of public transportation, shut down of establishments and apply work suspensions (Limos, 2020). In General Community Quarantine (GCQ), the government implemented a more relaxed measures and less restriction compared to ECQ, with public transportations and selected businesses allowed to operate in reduced capacity (Quieta, 2020). In some areas, Modified Enhanced Community Quarantine (MECQ) were implemented where the movement is limited within zone for obtaining essential goods and services and work, with no public transport but biking and non-motorized transport is encouraged. According to Quadra (2020), areas with low risk of coronavirus infection were placed under Modified General Community Quarantine (MGCQ) which is the most relaxed lockdown level, where minors and seniors or those at high risk for contracting the COVID-19 disease are required to stay home. Additionally, public transport is allowed but with strict social distancing as well as schools allowed to operate in limited face-to-face or in-person classes in strict with the minimum public health standards and consultations with the local government units (LGUs) and guidelines set by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED).

Several studies were conducted to determine the types of adverse effects of undergoing quarantine on individuals. Wu et al. (2020) revealed that psychological consequences of quarantine, like frustration, loneliness, and worries about the longer term are well-known risk factors for several mental disorders, including anxiety, affective disorders, and psychoses. Moreover, expected psychosocial and emotional responses to the observed pandemic are also different among students and adults as a result of specific restriction on minors, as an estimated 10–20% of adolescents globally experience mental state conditions, yet these remain under diagnosed and undertreated. Multiple factors determine mental state outcomes. The more risk factors adolescents are exposed to, the greater the potential impact on their psychological state (WHO, 2019). In a KFF Tracking Poll conducted in mid-July, it was reported that adults in the United States has experienced more stress and worry, increased alcohol consumption, and difficulty in eating and sleeping as an impact of the corona virus (Panchal et al., 2020).

Impact Assessment of Prolonged Quarantine on Senior High School Students in a State College in Zamboanga City, Philippines

In the study of Tee et al. (2020), the prevalence of psychiatric symptoms was examined and identified the factors contributing to psychological impact in the Philippines through online surveys that were gathered from March 28-April 12, 2020. The data gathered reported that Filipinos have moderate-to-severe symptoms of depression, anxiety and stress. More so, it was found that women were significantly associated with greater psychological impact of the pandemic and higher levels of stress, anxiety and depression.

Since Zamboanga City implemented different levels of community quarantine status and students became one of its casualties, this study was conceived to determine the impacts of prolonged quarantine on senior high school students in a State College in Zamboanga City, Philippines. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What are the impacts of prolonged quarantine on senior high school students in a State College in Zamboanga City, Philippines?
2. Is there a significant difference in the level of psychological effect of prolonged quarantine among senior high school students when data were grouped according to
 - a. Sex
 - b. Grade Level
 - c. Track

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed descriptive-quantitative research design. Survey method was utilized to determine the impact of prolonged quarantine on senior high school students in a State College in Zamboanga City, Philippines.

Respondents of the Study

There were 200 senior high school students participated in this study. The respondents were selected through total enumeration. Table 1 shows the demographic profile of the respondents.

Table 1. Demographic Profile of Senior High School Students

Variabes	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Sex		
Male	107	54
Female	93	46
Year Level		
Grade 11	72	36
Grade 12	128	64
Track		
Academic	110	55
TVL	90	45

Research Instrument

The researchers utilized the Prolonged Quarantine Impact Questioner (PQIQ). It is a researcher-made 5-point likert scale with 20 items. The PQIQ was validated by a Psychology Instructor and 2 Guidance Designates from public schools. The PQIQ was pilot tested with 30 non-participant students and obtained a Cronbach alpha value of .87 which indicates a great level of reliability.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers sought permission from the senior high school principal. Upon approval, the researchers distributed the PQIQ in Google forms through private messages using messenger and the students answered the PQIQ in their convenience. The duration of the assessment lasted for four weeks (December 23- January 15).

Data Analysis

Mean was used to determine the impact of prolonged quarantine on students. T-test was utilized to compare the level of psychological effect of prolonged quarantine when data were grouped according to sex, grade level and track.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Prolonged community quarantine has an impact to every individual. Table 2 shows the impact of prolonged community quarantine on senior high school students.

Impact Assessment of Prolonged Quarantine on Senior High School Students in a State College in Zamboanga City, Philippines

Table 2. Psychological Effect of Prolonged Community Quarantine among Senior High School Students

Indicators	Mean	Description	Rank
I feel anxious about getting COVID-19.	3.05	Often	15
I have been more expressive with my emotions whether those emotions are positive or negative.	3.01	Sometimes	17
I have episodes of different emotions during the quarantine.	3.24	Sometimes	8
I met new people and established new relationships.	3.01	Sometimes	16
I have experienced feelings of distress and emptiness.	3.17	Sometimes	11
I explored outside my area of interest and learned new things and acquired new skills.	3.24	Sometimes	7
I feel detached with my body.	2.62	Sometimes	20
I have coped/adapted with the changes of living in a quarantined life style.	3.36	Sometimes	6
I feel stressed and restless during the quarantine.	3.18	Sometimes	10
I have been spending more time with myself.	4.05	Often	2
I have experienced feelings of social isolation or loneliness.	3.09	Sometimes	14
I invest my time by finding new hobbies to do.	3.47	Sometimes	5
I became obsessed in thinking about things that are unwelcome and made me do or fix that certain things or thought.	3.12	Sometimes	13
I maintained and strengthened my relationship with my family and friends.	3.99	Often	3
I have experienced intense wave of fear characterized by its unexpectedness and debilitating, immobilizing intensity.	2.78	Sometimes	19
I became more relaxed.	3.16	Sometimes	12
I have experienced the feeling of being pressured during the recent quarantine.	3.24	Sometimes	9
I feel motivated to do exercise.	2.91	Sometimes	18
I have changes my sleeping pattern.	3.69	Often	4
I have become more faithful to God.	4.50	Always	1

It can be seen that prolonged community quarantine has different impact on students. Among the possible impacts listed in PQIQ, becoming more faithful to God obtained the highest mean score of 4.50. This indicate that students strengthen their faith to God by praying for the end of the pandemic and for protection of their family from the Covid-19. More so, engaging in spritual activities has a positive impact towards mental health and wellbeing (Cornah, 2006). The indicator spending more time for their selves obtained the second highest mean score of 4.05. Thus, students show self-care. According to Gleeson (2020), the current situation allows an individual to have more time on fixing and focusing themselves. Strengthening the relationship with family and friends obtained the third highest mean score of 3.99. Due to lockdown, there was limited movement of people. Thus, students can spend time to their family and friends. This findings affirmed the study of Alhas (2020), that pandemic allows oneself to spend more time with the members of the family. Changes in sleeping pattern obtained the fourth highest mean score of 3.69. Students spend most their time in watching movies and playing online games. This findings concur the idea of Martinelli (2021), where sleeping pattern change and sleeping quality was reduced. Students also expressed that during the quarantine period, they invested their time in new hobbies with a mean score 3.47. According to Martinelli (2021), lack of activity allow individuals to find new hobbies and activities to make themselves productive.

The result obtained in the impact of prolonged quarantine on senior high school students were grouped according to sex, grade level and track to determine if significant difference exist. Table 3 shows the T-test result in sex, grade level and track.

Table 3. Impact of Prolonged Quarantine According to Sex, Grade Level and Track

Variables	Mean Rank	T-Value	Significant Value	Interpretation
Sex				
Male	3.47	1.299	0.223*	Significant
Female	3.48			
Grade Level				
11	3.55	0.280	0.780*	Significant
12	3.41			
Track				
Academic	3.46	0.159	0.875*	Significant
TVL	3.47			

Impact Assessment of Prolonged Quarantine on Senior High School Students in a State College in Zamboanga City, Philippines

In terms on sex, it can be seen that it obtained a T-value of 1.299, with a significant value of 0.223, which is greater than α 0.05, thus, there is a significant difference on the impact of prolonged quarantine between male and female. The result further implied that more female (Mean = 3.48) experienced different impacts of prolonged quarantine than male (Mean=3.47).

In terms on grade level, it can be seen that it obtained a T-value of 0.280, with a significant value of 0.780, which is greater than α 0.05, thus, there is significant difference on the impact of prolonged quarantine between Grade 11 and 12 students. The result further implied that more Grade 11 students (Mean = 3.55) experienced different impacts of prolonged quarantine than Grade 12 students (Mean = 3.40).

In terms on track, it can be seen that it obtained a T-value of 0.159, with a significant value of 0.875 which is greater than α 0.05, thus, there is a significant difference on the impact of prolonged quarantine between academic and TVL students. The result further implied that more TVL students (Mean = 3.47) experienced different impacts of prolonged quarantine than academic track students (Mean = 3.46).

CONCLUSION

The implementation of prolonged quarantine has an impact on the lives of senior high school students such as strengthening their faith in God, spending time to their selves, family and friends, changes in sleeping pattern and investing time to new habits. More so, there was a significant difference in the impact of prolonged quarantine on senior high school students when data were grouped according to sex, grade level and track.

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Impact Assessment of Prolonged Quarantine on Senior High School Students in a State College in Zamboanga City, Philippines

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